

LINGUA-CULTURAL ASPECTS OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING IN THE EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract: This article presents research on linguocultural aspects and their use of foreign language teaching in the educational environment.

Keywords: Cross cultural communication, lingua-cultural aspect, cultural components, lingua-cultural ability, intercultural contact.

One of the most crucial aspects of every civilization is language. It is the means by which people connect with one another, form bonds, and form a sense of belonging. Language is important in learning and teaching culture as well as forming the thoughts of the younger generation. It is connected with cross cultural communication. Cross cultural communication is becoming increasingly crucial at the dawn of the twenty-first century. However, knowing a foreign language is insufficient to communicate effectively with people from other cultures. As we all know, one of the most important functions of language is the cumulative function, which means that it serves as a link between generations; it stores and transmits extra linguistic collective experience, as the language not only reflects current culture but also preserves all previous stages. ¹Lingua-cultural aspect is a discipline that, on the one hand, combines language acquisition and, on the other hand, provides specific knowledge about the country of the studied language. ²Linguacultural studies' major goal is to develop communicative skills for cross-cultural communication and to investigate those linguistic and extra linguistic events that most vividly express the national characteristics of a foreign culture. That is, our primary goal is to acquire the baseline information required for effective cross-cultural communication. As a

¹ Tomakhin G.D. Background knowledge as the main subject of linguistic and regional studies in. lang. at school, 2010.

² Tseng, Y.A. Lesson in Culture. ELT. 2002.

result, lingua-cultural competence encompasses not only the study of language (to build language, communicative, and linguistic competence) and linguistic elements in practice, but also the study of language as a cultural phenomenon. To comprehend the differences between the cultural-historical context and the national character of world languages, as well as the significance of language units as cultural components. This is where:

- Socio-cultural background – peculiarities of communication within the society, social behavior, social values, conversation formulae, non-verbal communication;
- Ethno-cultural background, which includes information about the way of life, traditions, holidays, and so on;
- Semiotic background, which includes information about the way of life, traditions, holidays, and so on;
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Students should form the following things in order to gain lingua-cultural competence:

- Linguacultural knowledge is a practice that is summarized as a language shape and described in terms of mind (the words, phrases, phrasal verbs, tongue-twister and in the shape of literary texts). Linguacultural knowledge encompasses knowledge about a country's history, culture, and traditions, as well as the characteristics of residents' communicative languages and social lives.
- Lingua-cultural ability to assess lingua-cultural information encoded in linguistic signals, as well as the creative application of lingua-cultural knowledge, combining theoretical knowledge and abilities.

³ Arlan M. A. "Linguistic and regional studies in teaching foreign languages in high school." Foreign languages at school №1 – 2000.

-The ability of students to accept knowledge and cultural phenomena is a personal quality.⁴

Because text functioning is so crucial in the actual practice of teaching foreign languages, V.V.Krasny's work contains a wealth of material on the subject. Yu.E.Prohorov's work provides a new qualitative basis for the content of texts as language units. The author considered text to be a means of communication, which results in the following compound phenomenon:

- a vision of cultures and traditions of one specific nation, the phenomenon of language, and extralinguistic reality;
- the shape of psychological life of persons;
- the fruit of one specific historical period and the form of existence of specific culture.

Students can take vital information about local cultural values whose language they study through texts since they have such a broad awareness of the functionality and content capacity of writings. The communicative upbringing and sociocultural stereotypes of language communication are the most essential among them in teaching foreign language lesson plans. Through visual and reading materials, students who are learning a foreign language become acquainted with the lives, customs, and traditions of the people whose language they are studying. Some scientists viewed communicative parenting as the norms of precise people's behaviors and the collecting of their traditions. They believed that communicative upbringing should be taught alongside foreign language learning habits on a receptive and productive foundation. The comparative description of the types of communicative upbringing in Russia and other countries will assist teachers in

⁴ Arlan M. A. "Linguistic and regional studies in teaching foreign languages in high school." Foreign languages at school №1 – 2000.

drawing students' attention to the differences that will arise in cultural debates, thereby assisting learners in developing their communicative abilities.⁵

Yu.E. Prohorov described stereotypes as a collection of linguistic mental units that can be found in a typical communicative process within a single nation. In reality, a stereotype is a certain nation's normative socio-cultural communication unit. The knowledge acquired through linguacultural text study is of immeasurable worth in terms of expanding young people's individual cognitive thinking, enriching their cultural fund, and greatly increasing their creative mastery. Students should accept all units of language cultural texts equally and organize them as a precise discourse in order to communicate. As we all know, the second sort of English instruction takes place mostly in schools. Teachers' main goal nowadays is to take into account students' acceptance of lingua-cultural competencies and to draw students' attention to the key objective qualities of the linguistic environment in which they learn during the teaching process. First and foremost, it is the original use of sociopolitical and literary texts, as well as the use of literary films, songs, and other internet information. There is no doubt that using such supplementary materials necessitates the teacher's most thorough preparation. However, it will draw pupils' attention to the subject and boost their enthusiasm for it.⁶

As a result, the primary purpose of linguistic and regional studies is to assure communicative competence in acts of intercultural contact, particularly through accurate perception of the interlocutor's speech and the creation of original texts for native speakers. Linguistic regional studies address a number of issues, including the basic philological issue of proper text comprehension, and so serve as a linguistic foundation not just for linguodidactics but also for translation. After all, in order to translate, one must first thoroughly comprehend a foreign text, including all nuances

⁵ Bakirova H.B. Some features of learning terminology in foreign language lessons. Chet tillarini o'rgatishning turlicha yondashuvlari: muammo va yechimlar xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferensiya materiallari. -Jizzax. 2021.

⁶ Kramersch, C. Language and Culture. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2007.

of meaning such as subtext, allusions, and allusions, and then find acceptable equivalents in the target language, taking into account the addressee.⁷

In conclusion, when teaching a foreign language, the goal of teaching culture is to impart to the student a minimum of background knowledge that a native speaker has. Such information, which is primarily related to geography, history, social life, art and culture, customs and traditions of the language's target nation, can be provided in the form of an Uzbek or English commentary. Thus, lingua-cultural aspects are firmly embedded as an important component of foreign language instruction.

REFERENCES

1. Arlan M. A. "Linguistic and regional studies in teaching foreign languages in high school." Foreign languages at school №1 – 2000.
2. Bakirova H.B. Some features of learning terminology in foreign language lessons. Chet tillarini o'rgatishning turlicha yondashuvlari: muammo va yechimlar xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferensiya materiallari. -Jizzax. 2021.
3. Corbett, J. An Intercultural Approach to English Language Teaching. Multilingual Matters Ltd, 2003.
4. Hughes, G. Culture in the Classroom, An argument for culture analysis in the second language classroom. Cambridge University Press, 2001.
5. Kramsch, C. Language and Culture. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2007.
6. Tomaxhin G.D. Background knowledge as the main subject of linguistic and regional studies in. lang. at school, 2010.
- Tseng.Y.A. Lesson in Culture. ELT. 2002

⁷ Corbett, J. An Intercultural Approach to English Language Teaching. Multilingual Matters Ltd, 2003.